

Netzsch DSC

In this guideline the steps required to integrate a Netzsch DSC 214 into the Chemotion ELN. This procedure enables remote access to the DSC's computer, which runs the vendor's software, and the procedure to transfer experiment data to the Chemotion ELN's inbox.

Considering all the [general preparation aspects](#), this procedure has been conducted on the following system configurations. However, it is likely to work on systems with different software versions as well.

Specifications of the DSC PC

- Operating system: Windows 10
- Software Name: NETZSCH Messung v.8.0.3
- Connected to Internet/Intranet: Yes
- Data files generated: Excel files
- Static IP address has been configured

Objectives

- Remote Device Control
- Data transfer to Chemotion ELN inbox

For the DSC device integration, we have decided to configure both of these features.

Configurations

Remote Device Control

General guidelines regarding the configurations of remote device control can be found [here](#).

Data transfer

Data will automatically be transferred to the Chemotion ELN once the data has been saved locally on the computer. The user only needs to make sure to name the output file according to the [naming convention](#) before saving it to the local machine.

Configurations in DSC PC

The DSC PC and the Chemotion ELN both need access to a common network storage location. This can be set up on a third-party storage (a NAS server, shared storage of another PC, etc.) or it can be set up locally on the DSC PC. In this case, the LSDF storage service from KIT has been used.

We need to download an executable file from the EFW builder that will run on the computer to transfer data from a predefined source (local location on the computer) to a destination (LSDF server in this case) and schedule a task at startup so that the process keeps running on the computer. Details can be found [here](#).

In this step, we have to restart the PC for the scheduler to run.

Configurations in Chemotion ELN

The Chemotion ELN's data collector has to be configured to collect data of the DSC device from the network location.

As for the file collector mechanism, there are two options.

- Collecting attachment files from emails
- Collecting files or folders from local drives or over SCP

Here in this guide, we have used the second mechanism where the files are collected from remote storage locations and are distributed to specific users based on the file-name matching the name abbreviation of the user. You can find details [here](#).